

1. Main categories of costs and potential savings which would be associated with using disposable cardboard ballot boxes in future

Traditional ballot boxes for government elections were constructed of metal and were stored for reuse. Although the ballot boxes were adapted to nest for storage and shipping, storage and shipping costs were considerable. It was therefore proposed to provide a disposable corrugated cardboard ballot box to be shipped flat and assembled at the polls. On the other hand, we have considered Deficiencies including lack of structural integrity necessary to ensure that ballots were not removed or inserted in an unauthorized manner. A feature of the cardboard ballot boxes is that fold lines have been minimalized so that production of the blank is less expensive and assembly of the tune ballot box is facilitated. Another feature of the cardboard ballot boxes is the provision of a container that cannot be accessed without leaving traces of the interrelation thereby, ensuring the integrity of the ballot count. The cost benefits of this container over rigid reusable containers will be apparent since the folded blank can be stored and shipped in a compact form and readily assembled for use. Since the ballot box is inexpensive it can be cut open to remove ballots and discarded thereby eliminating return shipping and storage costs. In accordance with the present disposable cardboard ballot boxes, there is provided a container for use in containing ballots comprising a front wall, a partial top wall closure integrally joined to said Front wall at an upper edge, an upstanding aperture handle on said partial top wall closure, a full top wall closure portion underlying and adhesively secured to said partial top wall, a rear wall integrally jointly to said top closure member and to a bottom wall, said bottom wall being in turn integrally joined along a remaining longitudinal edge to said front wall, said top wall, said front bottom and rear walls having side panels hinged joined thereto whereby first, second, third and fourth panels provided on snide edges of the said front wall, said bottom wall, said rear wall and said top wall close a sidewall of said container. and similar panels on opposed side edges, fold inwardly to close a remaining sidewall of said container, one or more tabs on a side edge of a selected one of the said front wall or said back wall to co-operate with slots at a side edge of a selected associated one of So id front or said rear panels. The present disposable cardboard ballot boxes also provides a novel blank for a ballot box said blank comprising a partial closure panel purloin, aperture to provide a handle, integrally joined along a fold line to a first panel, a side edge of said first panel having first and second side panels integrally joined thereto along fold lines, a ballot slot in one said side panel, a remaining edge of said first panel having a second panel integrally joined along fold line said second panel having side panels integrally joined alongside edges thereof, a third panel joined to a remaining edge of said second panel along a fold line, side edges of said third panel each having side panels integrally joined along fold lines at the side edges thereof, outer side edges of one said side panel having one or more tabs integrally joined thereto to cooperate with slots provided adjacent the fold lines at one of the side edges of said first panel and slots suitable for passage of ballots into sand ballot box in d selected side panel of said first panel to positioned over a slot in one the side panels of a side panel of said third panel when the ballot box is assembled and a fourth panel integrally joined to a remaining edge of said third panel along a fold line and having side panels integrally joined to side edges thereof along fold lines. So to summarize the design view in order to understand the cost better disposable cardboard ballot boxes for use in receiving ballots, comprising a front wall, a partial top wall closure, integrally joined to said front wall at an upper edge, an aperture handle on said partial top wall closure, a full top wall closure portion underlying and adhesively secured to said partial top wall a rear wall integrally joined to said top closure member and to a bottom wall, said bottom wall being in turn integrally joined along a remaining longitudinal edge to said front wall, said top-wall, said front bottom and rear walls having panels hingedly joined thereto whereby first, second, third and fourth panels provided on side edges of said front wall, said bottom wall, said rear wall and said top wall close a side wall of said container and similar panels on opposed side edge fold inwardly to close a remaining side wall of said container and one or more tabs on a side edge of a selected one of said front wall or said back wall

to co-operate with slots at a side edge of a selected associated one of said front or said rear panels on the other hand additionally a handle includes a portion cut out of the panel and bent back on itself along a fold line. An integral blank for a ballot box, said blank comprising a partial closure panel portion apertured to provide a handle integrally joined along a fold line to a first panel, side edges of said first panel having first and second side panels integrally joined thereto along fold lines, a ballot slot in one said side panel, a remaining edge of said first panel having a second panel integrally joined along a fold line including side panels integrally joined alongside edges thereof, a third panel joined to a remaining edge of said second panel along a fold line, side edges of said third panel each having side panels integrally joined along fold lines at the side edges thereof, outer side edges of one said side panel having one or more tabs integrally joined thereto to cooperate with slots provided adjacent the fold lines at a selected one of the side edges of said first panel and a slot suitable for passage of ballots into said ballot box in a selected side panel of said first panel to communicate with a slot in one the side panels of a side panel of said third panel when the ballot box is assembled and a fourth panel integrally joined to a remaining edge of said third panel along a fold line and having side panels integrally joined to side edges thereof along fold lines.^[1]

So cost wise manufactured from white-faced recyclable fluted board which during disposable it can be sale and generate revenue, must be supplied in flat (collapsed) form which minimize the cost of transportation, Assembly must not require the use of any tools or additional materials such as tape which save the cost for assembler and maintenance, the Clear assembly instructions and/or diagrams printed on each item save money on training material for electoral bodies to how to assemble, robust construction able to hold and carry an internal load of 25 kg, without distorting, tearing or collapsing when lifted and transported can hold estimate of 5000 ballot paper of A4 of 80gsm or in other word the box when assembled must be of a size capable of holding for any gram of standard paper 1,700 A4 size ballot papers (folded) with 30% of the capacity spare – approximately 0.07 cubic meters (70 liters) total capacity which save money on purchasing of number of ballot boxes.^[2]

2. Main categories of costs which would be associated with continuing to use and store metal boxes

When we look at the cost of the continuing to use and store metal boxes we can view that as starting of generally an average of 30% metal Ballot boxes misses between elections because of the storing problem which leads for each election year to purchase to fill the gaps of those missing metal ballot boxes. On the other hand maintenance of the ballot box is also so cost including painting and cleaning for each coming. ^[3] The cost of storing metal boxes is also huge between election periods which is a waste of space and money. On the other hand Durable of the metal ballot box Where durable ballot boxes are used, proper maintenance is important: in ensuring that they are all retrieved from voting stations; that regular stocktakes are undertaken; that they are regularly inspected in storage; necessary repairs are made or replacements obtained which generally cost a fortune. When we view regarding Ballot Box Quantities, Quantities of metal ballot boxes required at each voting station will depend on several factors in the legal and procedural framework, the number of voters expected; the size of the ballot; the capacity of the ballot box; the number of different ballots to be completed or separate elections being held simultaneously; whether the voting station is split into different polling streams for different polling subdivisions. But despite all of the above because of the design to maximize the number of the vote to be accompanying and its weight might lead to higher costs. ^[4]

Tamper-proof sealing of ballot boxes is one of the basic guarantees of voting integrity. Ballot boxes must be sealed from the commencement of voting through to their opening, after the close of voting, for removal of ballot boxes for the count. Where ballot boxes are also used as the container for transporting accountable materials to the voting station and from the count back to the electoral management body, they will also need to be sealed for these shipments. One method of sealing ballot boxes could be a uniquely numbered keyed lock or locks. It is appropriate to seal, with a paper seal, wax, or some other method, over the keyhole of each lock when it is affixed to the ballot box. Another method could be uniquely numbered plastic or nylon security tied seals. Numbered plastic security tied seals are effective and generally more practicable. Whether plastic security ties or traditional locks are used, these are accountable items that should be maintained securely, and their use on each ballot box used in voting stations accurately recorded. Where disposable ballot boxes are used, assembly joints may be further secured by the use of security tape. The quantities of seals required will depend on the number and design of ballot boxes. Durable ballot boxes would normally have two sealing points, on a hinged lid and a sealing slide on the slot. Designs for disposable ballot boxes of two-piece construction (separate lid) would normally have four sealing points (at each top corner). Those of single-piece construction (fold-down lid) would have two sealing points. Sufficient seals must be on hand in each voting station to cover all sealing points for all required sealing and re-sealing of the boxes. Also when we use the metal boxes every election year we have to purchase separately a tamper-proof sealing. ^[5]

Reference List

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